

Soil organic carbon stocks in Vojvodina, Serbia: Establishing a reference system for natural and semi-natural ecosystems areas

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ABSTRACT

Natural and semi-natural soils are essential benchmarks for carbon accounting and restoration planning, yet they remain critically under-represented in regional and European soil datasets, particularly in intensively used agricultural settings of Southeast Europe. In the Pannonian Basin, existing soil monitoring systems focus predominantly on arable land, creating a major data gap for natural and semi-natural reference states required for climate mitigation reporting and digital soil mapping. This study addresses this gap by establishing the first natural-soil reference system for remnant natural and semi-natural ecosystems of Vojvodina (Serbia), where less than 10% of original steppe–forest–wetland habitats persist. Using a spatially explicit, machine-learning-assisted sampling framework, we identified 62 representative forest and grassland locations and collected 186 soil samples following harmonized international protocols. Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) stocks were quantified and analyzed across spatial clusters. Average SOC stocks were higher in grasslands than in forests, with variation driven primarily by soil texture, aridity gradients, and land-cover type. Comparison with historical datasets (1950–1960) revealed a consistent SOC decline across all clusters. Machine-learning models achieved moderate predictive performance for continuous SOC estimation, while classification into SOC categories showed stronger performance. Results showed significant mismatches between global SOC datasets and locally derived measurements, underscoring the necessity of regionally calibrated reference systems. The proposed spatially stratified sampling methodology ensures proportional representation of environmental strata and provides a scalable framework for soil monitoring in heterogeneous landscapes, strengthening carbon accounting under land use frameworks, and supports EU Soil Mission 2030 and nature-based climate solutions.

1. Introduction

About 33% of the world's land is degraded, accompanied by notable losses of soil organic carbon (SOC) (Shukla et al., 2019). SOC is widely recognized as a key indicator of soil health and one of the major terrestrial carbon pools, playing a critical role in ecosystem functioning, climate regulation, and agricultural productivity (Deb et al., 2015; Lal, 2016; Ngatia et al., 2021). Monitoring SOC reserves and their temporal changes is critical for climate change mitigation and greenhouse gas (GHG) reporting. In particular, SOC quantification represents a key component of the Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) emission inventory (Penman et al., 2003), which supports transparent reporting under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) (Vasin et al., 2024). To improve harmonization of

soil monitoring, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) introduced in 2020 a *Protocol for Measuring, Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification of Organic Matter in Agricultural Soils* (FAO, 2020). In parallel, European initiatives such as the EU Land use/cover area frame survey (LUCAS) Soil module (Fernandez-Ugalde et al., 2022) aim to provide standardized soil data across the continent.

Beyond carbon storage, healthy soil provides essential ecosystem services, including food production, freshwater supply, and flood prevention (Brady and Weil, 2008; Wang, 2022). Consequently, soil protection and restoration have become increasingly important priorities for environmental policy and land management strategies. Despite growing recognition of soil degradation challenges, policy frameworks often remain constrained by insufficient data and monitoring tools to support evidence-based decision-making (Kibblewhite et al., 2012;

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Turpin et al., 2017; Ronchi et al., 2019). Recent initiatives, including the EU Soil Mission and international soil monitoring programs, emphasize the need for improved soil data infrastructures and harmonized methodologies that enable reliable assessment of soil condition and ecosystem services (Martinho et al., 2024). In this context, the development of regionally representative soil reference datasets is critical for strengthening the scientific basis of policy implementation and supporting nature-based climate solutions.

Natural and semi-natural soils serve as critical benchmarks for assessing soil condition, ecosystem restoration potential, and climate adaptation strategies (Arrouays et al., 2021; Assad et al., 2013; Wiśniewski and Märker, 2021). However, their systematic characterization remains largely confined to Western Europe and North America (Batjes et al., 2020). The lack of data is particularly evident in the Pannonian Basin. Harmonized initiatives, such as the EU LUCAS Soil module, reveal a significant data deficit in this region, particularly for natural and semi-natural ecosystems (Fernandez-Ugalde et al., 2022). Vojvodina, Serbia's agricultural core, represents an extreme case of landscape transformation, with less than 10% of the original pristine steppe-forest-wetland mosaic remaining intact (EEA, 2022). Existing regional datasets, including the Serbian Soil Information System (Vidojević, 2015), focus exclusively on arable land, omitting reference states necessary for digital soil mapping (DSM), carbon accounting, and climate adaptation planning (Arrouays et al., 2021). The region of Vojvodina in northern Serbia represents a characteristic example of an intensively cultivated lowland landscape. Decades of crop production have resulted in an extremely low share of natural and semi-natural habitats (<20%) and limited afforestation (<15%) (Decision of the Provincial assembly, 2016; ESA, 2017). Despite this transformation, systematic soil monitoring in the region has historically focused only on agricultural soils. Three major soil data surveys have been conducted: the first was compiled in the 1950s–1960s during the creation of the first Soil Map of Vojvodina (scale 1:50,000) (Neigebauer et al., 1971), followed by two national soil campaigns in the early 1990s and in 2011–2013 (Vasin et al., 2022). The published studies based on these surveys report continuous decline in soil carbon pools across the region (Milić et al., 2011; Vasin et al., 2021). To date, no harmonized and spatially explicit soil reference system exists for natural and semi-natural ecosystems in Vojvodina.

To address this gap this study established the first reference system for Vojvodina's remnant natural and semi-natural ecosystems. The framework is developed to be compliant with the World Reference Base (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2022), aligned with the objectives of EU Soil Mission (EU Mission, 2021), consistent with the Serbia's National Action Plan (2023–2030) (Climate change adaptation programme for, 2024) and scalable to other data-poor transitional landscapes.

The overall objective of the study is to reveal and quantify SOC stocks in natural and semi-natural habitats embedded within intensively cultivated landscapes (green infrastructure) and to provide baseline data for carbon accounting, restoration planning, and nature-based climate solutions. Beyond generating new SOC measurements, this study also develops and tests a spatially explicit methodological framework that combines stratified sampling, spatial clustering, and standardized laboratory analyses to establish natural soil reference systems in data-poor agricultural landscapes on regional, NUTS2 level.

Specifically, the study aims to:

- develop a landscape-scale stratified sampling scheme for representative site selection and proportional soil sampling across land-cover types
- measure soil organic carbon to understand the condition of the soil ecosystem within natural and semi-natural areas
- evaluate the interaction between natural infrastructure heterogeneity and SOC distribution
- scale the applicability of global regression models at the NUTS2 level
- understand how in-situ data correspond to the historical NUTS2 level

- develop geographically explicit and harmonized carbon registries.

To achieve the objectives of the study, we developed a combination of spatially explicit landscape-scale sampling methodologies for soil assessment, supported by machine-learning-assisted analyses. Our approach integrates (i) novel stratified and (ii) proportional sampling schemes, (iii) standardized physical and chemical analyses, (iv) evaluation of landscape management and heterogeneity, as well as adapted methods for (v) SOC stock prediction and (vi) intercomparison of in situ data with existing databases. Existing protocols, such as the EU LUCAS framework, were used to guide the design (Ballin et al., 2022; Guerra et al., 2021; FAOLEX Data Base).

By integrating spatially structured sampling, harmonized analytical protocols, and regional baseline assessment, this study provides the first comprehensive and harmonized SOC dataset for natural and semi-natural ecosystems in Vojvodina, representing, to our knowledge, the first reference baseline for such ecosystems in the Pannonian lowlands. The proposed framework combines spatial stratification with a clustering-based sampling design, enabling representative coverage of fragmented natural habitats within intensively cultivated landscapes at the regional (NUTS2) scale. The resulting dataset supports the development of a regional natural-soil reference system and is compatible with emerging European soil data infrastructures, including initiatives linked to the EU Soil Mission. More broadly, this methodological approach offers a scalable pathway for establishing natural soil reference systems in other data-poor and highly transformed agricultural regions.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The Vojvodina region (Fig. 1g) comprises a complex mosaic of agricultural, steppe, and forest zones (Galić et al., 2009; Pavlović et al., 2017). Land use is dominated by arable land (81.25%), followed by meadows (9.36%), gardens (6.25%), and pastures (3.13%). The most prevalent soil type is chernozem, covering 40.63% of the area, followed by semigley and humogley (18.75% each), fluvisol (9.36%), and solonchak and solonetz (6.25% each) (Sekulić et al., 2010; Nešić et al., 2015). The long-term mean annual precipitation in Vojvodina ranges between 550 and 600 mm, with a west-to-east gradient from ~650 mm to below 500 mm, and increased frequencies of drought events and longer dry spell durations (Djurdjević et al., 2024; Filipović et al., 2025). This region is characterized by traditional intensive agricultural production, extensive use of artificial fertilizers, and limited agrotechnology, resulting in significant soil degradation, reduced carbon sequestration capacity, disrupted soil water profiles, and improper agricultural land management. Serbia is currently ranked the most vulnerable European country to climate change (Rank countries by ND, 2023). As such, this region is chosen as the one in which applying LULUCF-related diversity measures can make a significant advancement.

2.2. Overview of the proposed framework

The proposed methodological framework was developed to support a comprehensive assessment of SOC stocks across natural and semi-natural areas, combining field sampling, laboratory analysis, spatial data processing, and ML-based modelling (Fig. 2). To support balanced and representative sampling across representative land-cover types, we designed a spatially explicit ML-assisted sampling proportional soil sampling strategy, which constitutes the core methodology of this study. Thus, the selection of sampling areas was conducted using ML techniques, incorporating spatial clustering and optimization to identify representative sites. At each location, we identified three composite soil sampling sites (plots) using the SoilBon methodology Fig. S1(a and b)

Fig. 1. Spatial distribution of all LUCAS sampling locations in Europe (a), shown separately for the survey years 2009 (b), 2015 (c), 2018 (d), and 2022 (e), and the spatial distribution of all LUCAS sampling locations for Serbia (f), and Vojvodina with a 1 km × 1 km LUCAS grid (g) (LUCAS, 2025) *In Serbia, the LUCAS methodology included soil sampling only in 2015 for selected soil parameters, but these data are still not publicly available.

based on (Guerra et al., 2021). Leveraging on developed sampling strategy (Section 2.3), the study further included the analysis of soil physical and chemical properties (Section 2.4), the assessment of landscape management and heterogeneity (Section 2.5.), SOC stock prediction using both regression and classification approaches (Section 2.6), and the inter-comparison of the obtained results with existing soil information sources (Section 2.7).

Such comprehensive approach integrates the EU standardized Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey (LUCAS) methodology (Ballin et al., 2022) and other complementary methodologies for proportional soil sampling (Guerra et al., 2021; Rank countries by ND, 2023), standardized methodologies for soil laboratory analysis (Kašanin-Grubin et al., 2023), landscape heterogeneity assessment (Lucas Landscape Indicators), SOC stock prediction modelling (van Wesemael et al., 2024), and data inter-comparison (Brus et al., 2017). Thus the proposed framework ensures that all methodologies are aligned with the study objectives, enabling robust SOC estimation across multiple ecosystem types in Vojvodina.

2.3. Sampling strategy, design and effort

2.3.1. Location selection and spatial clusters identification

To ensure a systematic and stratified sampling strategy scheme for natural and semi-natural areas across the Vojvodina region, we applied the LUCAS methodology (Ballin et al., 2022). First, we overlaid the

Vojvodina region (NUTS2) with a 1 km × 1 km grid. We delineated and extracted natural and semi-natural areas using spatial information from the Copernicus LULC dataset (available via the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service portal). Second, we selected only areas with forest and grassland cover. To identify the clusters at the level where field sampling would be conducted, an exploration analysis was performed using our 1 km × 1 km fixed grid, with each grid cell represented by its central point. Based on this analysis, six groups (spatial clusters) were initially identified in forests (five of which were retained; see data below in 3.1.1), and six in grasslands. We used the following features: the sum of precipitation, average temperature at 2 m above ground, and minimum temperature from C3S Copernicus for the period from 2015 to 2024; and soil properties—order and type plus the proportions of silt, sand, and clay (Živković et al., 1972) to quantify areas with common denominators. The full dataset was first processed by removing irrelevant attributes, standardizing column names, filtering specific CORINE classes, and then re-encoding CORINE class labels into a simplified numerical range (0 to 5) for analysis.

In the second step, an unsupervised spatial clustering approach was applied to forests and grasslands, separately. A custom class, CorineClassClustering, was developed to perform clustering using the K-Prototypes algorithm (Huang, 1998), which handles both numerical and categorical variables. Data normalization was applied to numerical features using MinMax scaling. To determine the optimal number of clusters within each CORINE class, the Elbow method was used to

Fig. 2. Overview of the proposed methodological framework: (a) stratified sampling scheme with proportional sampling across representative land-cover types; (b) soil sampling design according to developed strategy; (c) standardized physical and chemical sample analyses and evaluation of landscape management and heterogeneity based on collected data; (d) data processing and inter-comparison with the existing data sources: SoilAtlas of Vojvodina (Živković et al., 1972), WorldSoils database (van Wesemael et al., 2024), and SoilGrids database (Poggio et al., 2021); (e) SOC prediction modelling and modelling soil properties.

calculate WCSS (Within-Cluster Sum of Squares) (Vysala and Gomes, 2020) across a range of cluster counts (1–10). Sampling locations were initially generated as 6,041 random points (potential locations) within the delineated area of natural and semi-natural types so that each represents the central point of a 1×1 km quadrat (Fig. 1g). From this number of points, 28.22% and 46.86% were within forest and grassland classes (3906), respectively. For each class, data was exported as individual GeoJSON files to facilitate modular processing. Once the optimal cluster number was selected, the data were clustered, and a stratified random sampling approach was used to select a fixed number of representative points per class while preserving internal cluster distribution. The resulting samples were stored and visualized for

downstream spatial and ecological analysis. Finally, the strata were identified, and sampling locations were systematically distributed to cover the entire territory in proportion to each stratum's type and size (see details below). It follows methodologies for proportional soil sampling across representative land-cover types (Guerra et al., 2021; FAO-LEX Data Base). To refine the number of generated sampling locations using the machine learning (ML) approach, we use Spatial Simulated Annealing (Vysala and Gomes, 2020) to allocate points within strata. The goal was to determine the best allocation of the predefined number of samples (app. 200 soil samples) to select the final set of locations within identified strata. These strata, defined by stratigraphical, compositional, and climatic variables, form the basis for robust and

spatially explicit estimation of carbon stock in natural and semi-natural areas that represent green infrastructure in the Vojvodina region.

2.3.2. Cluster naming in the developed sampling strategy

Following the exploratory analysis, we proceeded to name the clusters. The following data were used to inform the naming and characterization of the clusters. In this step, we combined three environmental descriptors for each cluster:

- Land cover –from our cluster classes groups,
- Soil characteristics – texture as a relatively stable inherent soil property
- Aridity – derived from the De Martonne Aridity Index (IDM) (de Martonne, 1942; Passarella et al., 2020) for the two periods 1950-1960 and 2015-2024, calculated using the approach from Hrnjak et al., 2014 (Hrnjak et al., 2014) (Equation (1)). IDM was calculated, following equation (2), for each sampling location, based on mean annual temperature (°C) and annual sum of precipitation (mm) through OpenMeteo portal (Open Meteo Portal).

$$IDM = P/T + 10 \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

where P represents the annual sum of precipitation (mm) and T is mean annual temperature (°C).

The IDM values were classified according to standard climatic categories. The complete values of IDM, along with corresponding aridity categories for each cluster are given in [Supplementary material S1](#) section 1.3 [Table S3](#) for two periods, 1950-1960 and 2015-2024.

2.3.3. Site selection within identified clusters

The initial sampling iteration, aimed at establishing a green infrastructure soil repository depicting regions' natural and semi-natural soil properties, was designed to reflect the proportional areal coverage of grassland and forest. The total number of samples ($n = 186$) was constrained by laboratory processing capacity for the full suite of selected parameters. Sampling locations were allocated proportionally to land cover representation within the study area (forests: 28.22%; grasslands: 46.86%), resulting in approximately 70 and 116 target samples, respectively.

According to Equation (2), subsequent sampling iterations will preserve the set proportional relationships to ensure consistent representation of each land cover type. As the total sample size increases, the sample numbers for each cluster i will be calculated as:

$$Ideal\ samples_i = \text{New total samples} \times (\text{Expected } \%_i / 100) \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

In the first iteration of the sampling campaign, a lower threshold sampling design was applied—comprising 56 forest and 94 grassland sampling sites—to establish a representative yet logistically feasible baseline for soil data collection. The use of a lower threshold at this stage enabled the research team to ([Supplementary material S1](#) section 1.1 and 1.2):

- Test the sampling protocol under field conditions,
- Evaluate spatial representativeness and accessibility, and
- Capture sufficient variability for the initial clustering analysis.

2.3.4. The soil sampling design and effort

The soil sampling design followed international standards (Ballin et al., 2022; Guerra et al., 2021), with two key adaptations to align it with the national scale methodology (FAOLEX Data Base). First, sampling depths were adjusted to ensure comparability with historical soil data and to account for drought conditions that may limit microbial activity in the topsoil. Second, the standard 1 km × 1 km quadrants were reduced to 100 m × 100 m to better capture the actual extent of natural habitats. In the intensively used landscapes of Vojvodina, a 1 km × 1 km quadrant does not always contain only natural areas, making this

adjustment necessary to ensure sampling is conducted within the true natural habitat patches. At each location, three samples were collected ([Fig. S1a](#)), one from each of the selected sampling plots representing the three sampling sites. Thus, each composite sample consisted of nine subsamples taken within a 30 m × 30 m plot ([Fig. S1b](#)). After clustering was completed, each resulting cluster was characterized and assigned an interpretable ecological label in an Integrated Cluster Description step. The three plots of 30 m × 30 m were positioned within a 100 m × 100 m area, which is 0.1 ha quadrants, following the approach in (Stolbovoy et al., 2006). With this sampling design, each cluster contained at least 6 samples, enabling the calculation of SOC stock at both the site and cluster levels. Because each composite sample was derived from the same surface extent, the design meets the recommended sampling density per area for SOC stock estimation proposed by Stolbovoy et al. (2006) (Stolbovoy et al., 2006).

Soil sampling was conducted at each site following a standardized SoilBon protocol (Guerra et al., 2021). One sampling location accounted for three types of samples: i) from the central point, a 0–30 cm bulk density sample was collected using Kopetzky cylinders, ii) an undisturbed soil monolith (30 cm × 30 cm × 30 cm) was extracted from the central point to assess soil structure, iii) a composite soil sample, obtained by homogenizing material collected from nine points within each plot (central point, four corners, and four midpoints), ensuring spatial representativeness for specific layers and analyses: a 0–1 cm surface crust sample, 1–30 cm sample for physical and chemical analyses and a 30 cm depth sample for eDNA analysis. In the final number of samples, all three types of samples collected from one sampling site are considered one sample ($n = 186$), corresponding to the same number of sampling locations. This subsampling design ensures robust spatial representation and supports a wide range of physical, chemical, and biological assessments. For this study, we used data from physical and chemical analyses, while eDNA analysis will be reported in follow-up work.

2.4. Soil properties across ecosystems

Soil physical and chemical properties were assessed using both disturbed and undisturbed samples following national and international protocols (Guerra et al., 2021; FAOLEX Data Base). Undisturbed samples ($\approx 100\text{ cm}^3$ Kopecky cylinders) were used to determine bulk density after oven drying at 105 °C while disturbed soil was sieved (<2 mm) to analyze 12 parameters¹ ([Table 1](#)). All analyses were conducted in the Laboratory for Soil, Fertilizer, and Plant Material Testing, following standardized methodologies for soil analysis (Kasanin-Grubin et al., 2023), at the Department of Pedology and Soil Water Regime, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad.

SOC stocks were estimated from bulk density (BD) and SOC content, considering sampling depth.

Site-level SOC stocks [t ha^{-1}] were estimated for 186 sites using an adapted Evrendilek and Wali (2001) method (Equation (3)) (Stolbovoy et al., 2006):

Table 1
Overview of the selected parameters for the analyses.

No.	Properties	Parameter
1	Textural	Soil texture
2	Structural	Aggregate stability
3	Structural	Water holding capacity
4	Structural	Soil structure coefficient (Ks)
5	Compositional	Soil pH
6	Compositional	CaCO ₃ content
7	Compositional	Soil organic carbon (SOC)
8	Compositional	Total nitrogen
9	Compositional	Available phosphorus (PO ₄ -P)
10	Compositional	Available potassium (K ₂ O)
11	Compositional	Cation exchange capacity (CEC)
12	Compositional	Total water-soluble salts

$$SOCstock_{site} = \sum_{site=1}^i (SOC \times BD \times Depth) \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

Where, $SOCstock_{site}$ is the amount of SOC stock at the sampling site derived from a composite sample [$g\ kg^{-1}$], SOC is the amount of organic carbon in soil [$g\ kg^{-1}$], BD is the bulk density [$Mg\ m^{-3}$], and $Depth$ is the sampling depth [m].

Long-term trends in SOC stock change were evaluated by comparing reference values from the historical Soil Atlas data (Živković et al., 1972) with measurements collected in 2024/2025. To ensure comparability between periods, SOC stock was calculated using the same equation (Equation (3)). For the historical Soil Atlas data from the 1950s (Živković et al., 1972), the original humus content values first had to be converted into SOC values using the commonly applied convention of dividing humus content by 1.72 (FAO, 2020; Lee et al., 2023). Once converted, these SOC values were inserted into the SOC stock formula (Equation (3)).

SOC stock reference values of the 2024/2025 dataset were calculated using newly obtained SOC and bulk density measurements for 0.1 ha plots ($30 \times 30\ m$) within each cluster, applying the same equation from (Stolbovoy et al., 2006).

$$SOCstock_{reference} = SOCstock_{mean} \times Ap \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

In this formulation, $SOCstock_{mean}$ represents the average SOC stock per sampling location, and Ap is the plot area (Stolbovoy et al., 2006). The same plot area was used to derive $SOCstock_{reference}$ values for the historical 1960 dataset. Using average SOC and BD values from historical sources (Živković et al., 1972), mean SOC stock per plot was calculated using the same adapted equation (Equation (4)). For historical measurements, we presumed that this allowed a direct comparison with individual SOC values linked to (Živković et al., 1972) spatial regions in which the plot samples of 2024/2025 campaign were located.

After averaging $SOCstock_{reference}$ values within each cluster, changes in SOC stock between periods were calculated using the following equation (Equation (5)).

$$\Delta SOCstock_{reference} = SOCstock_{reference_new} - SOCstock_{reference_old} \quad (\text{Equation 5})$$

We used in situ SOC values measured in forests and grasslands and compared them with SOC levels, from satellite-based and ML generated SOC map available in AgroSense farm management platform (Tagarakis et al., 2018) that farmers in Serbia freely use. To ensure consistency, humus values reported for crop fields were converted to SOC using the same conversion method described above. For this comparison, we selected the closest crop field locations situated approximately 1 km from our original natural and semi-natural sampling sites.

2.5. Landscape management and heterogeneity

To account for land management intensity, we overlapped the potential sampling locations with the spatial layer of protected areas and ecological network area (Regulation on Ecological Network, 2010). To measure landscape homogeneity or heterogeneity, we used the LUCAS guidelines (Ballin et al., 2022). We counted the number of distinct land covers and land uses along a 250m-long East-West transect in the center of a $1 \times 1\ km$ quadrant. According to the LUCAS approach, all visible land cover changes along the transect, including both areal classes and linear elements, were recorded and later summarized to ensure a consistent representation of different landscape types and to capture overall landscape heterogeneity. Linear elements identified along the transect included grass margins, shrubs, single trees, avenue trees, fences, roads, among others, while land cover classes included artificial land, various crop types, grassland, water bodies, and other features, as per the LUCAS methodology (Lucas Landscape Indicators).

The level of landscape heterogeneity can be directly expressed through diversity indicators.

The richness-diversity indicator is computed as the number of distinct land cover codes in each transect. The information on different types of land cover and their relative abundance (i.e., whether the same type of land cover recurs in a transect) can be summarized by means of two Shannon indices.

The Shannon Diversity Index (SDI) (Shannon and Weaver, 1949) accounts for both the total number of distinct land cover types (m) observed at one point and their relative proportions (P_i). It offers a more detailed description of area composition than simple richness, which reflects only the number of land cover types present.

$$SDI = - \sum_i^m (P_i \cdot \ln(P_i)) \quad (\text{Equation 6})$$

The Shannon Evenness Index (SEI) (Pielou, 1966) is calculated by dividing the SDI by its maximum possible value, $\ln(m)$. As a result, it ranges from 0 to 1, making it easier to interpret.

$$SEI = - \sum_i^m \frac{(P_i \cdot \ln(P_i))}{\ln(m)} \quad (\text{Equation 7})$$

2.6. SOC stock predictions

In this study, we applied both ML regression and classification approaches to estimate SOC stock, aiming to assess the influence of diverse land cover and soil-related features on SOC stock variability. Unlike studies based on soil reflectance and satellite-derived SOC predictions (van Wesemael et al., 2024), this study utilizes a data-driven, in-situ approach. Therefore, as input variables, we incorporated several groups of predictors:

- Diversity indicators - specifically Richness diversity, Shannon Diversity Index, and Shannon Evenness Index;
- Soil descriptors - including Soil texture, Soil type from (Živković et al., 1972), and the four main Soil groups in the Vojvodina region, which are based on geomorphology, water influence and physico-chemical properties obtained in the research by Ćirić et al. (2017) (Ćirić et al., 2017), and
- Spatial clusters - represented by derived cluster classes of grassland and forest areas.

Soil descriptors and spatial cluster variables were treated as categorical predictors and encoded through one-hot encoding to ensure compatibility with numerical variables. The initial dataset comprised 39 predictors. After decomposing the categorical variables, the total number of features increased to 72 (Supplementary material S section 1.4, Table S4.).

As mentioned, land cover types were recorded along a 250 m transect at each location. Forest and grassland samples were used together in modeling. SOC stock values from the three sites (plots), where composite soil sampling was conducted, were averaged per location. Consequently, from 186 soil samples, we got 62 SOC stock values used for this task. Fig. 3 presents the distribution of SOC stock values across all samples, represented by a histogram with an overlaid kernel density estimate (KDE).

2.6.1. Regression

The regression modeling aimed to determine the relative influence of environmental predictors on SOC stock. Several algorithms were tested, including Elastic Net (Zou and Hastie, 2005), Random Forest Regressor (Breiman, 2001), and CatBoost Regressor (Prokhorenkova et al., 2018). We tested Elastic Net since it provides a regularized linear baseline and handles multicollinearity. Random Forest Regressor was included due to its robustness and ability to model complex non-linear relationships. CatBoost Regressor was tested because it performs strongly on tabular data and efficiently handles categorical predictors without extensive

Fig. 3. Histogram with an overlaid kernel density estimate (KDE) across all samples.

preprocessing. Predictor selection was performed using Sequential Forward Selection (SFS), starting from default model parameters, with variables introduced one by one and the model re-evaluated at each iteration. The feature combination that achieved the best 5-fold cross-validated performance across 5 repeats was retained, and the process continued until no further improvement was observed. In the final stage, hyperparameter tuning was performed on the selected subset of predictors to optimize model performance. Model accuracy was quantified using 5 repeats of 5-fold cross-validation with the coefficient of determination (R^2) as the primary evaluation metric and the root mean squared error (RMSE) as a secondary metric when R^2 values were unchanged.

2.6.2. Classification

In the classification approach, the SOC stock was categorized into three levels: *low*, *medium*, and *high*. To establish thresholds for classifying SOC stock into these levels, the K-means clustering method (Lloyd, 1982; MacQueen, 1967) was applied to the observed SOC stock distribution. K-means clustering ($k = 3$) was used on the one-dimensional SOC stock values to identify three natural groupings corresponding to low, medium, and high SOC levels. The algorithm was initialized with 50 random starts to ensure stable centroid estimation, after which the sorted cluster centers were used to derive two threshold values at the midpoints between adjacent centroids. These thresholds were then used to assign each sample to its corresponding SOC stock class.

Three classification models were tested: Logistic Regression (Hosmer et al., 2013), Random Forest classifier (Breiman, 2001), and CatBoost classifier (Prokhorenkova et al., 2018). We tested Logistic Regression because it provides a simple, linear baseline for comparison, while Random Forest was included for its robustness and ability to capture non-linear relationships. The CatBoost classifier was tested because it efficiently handles datasets with numerous categorical features, making it well-suited for this type of data. As in the regression case, SFS was used to identify the most relevant predictors by sequentially adding variables to models with default parameters until no further meaningful improvement was observed. Feature selection and hyperparameter tuning were guided by stratified 5-fold cross-validation with 5 repeats,

using macro F1-score as the primary selection criterion and overall accuracy as a secondary metric when F1 values remained unchanged.

2.7. Inter-comparison with the existing soil data

Although collected soil samples provided the basis for SOC stock predictions using the newly designed regression and classification models, measured SOC values were also compared with available soil datasets for the selected region. Through inter-comparison with SOC measurements and estimates from three different data sources, the collected SOC data were analyzed in the context of:

- Accuracy of the existing historical measurements, which were intermittently collected by different types of studies and over a long period of several decades.
- Accuracy and validity of alternative SOC estimates provided by the existing global prediction models over selected areas of interest, for which the available ground-truth data were usually lacking; and
- The necessity of developing new SOC prediction maps and updating existing soil datasets for the selected region.

This was performed by a developed statistical framework in which the individual geo-referenced SOC values from this study were associated with the type of available SOC information that was spatially closest to the newly collected SOC samples. More information and the specific details of the conducted analyses can be found in the corresponding supplementary document “Supplementary S2 - SOC Data Analysis Report - Inter-Comparison with SoilAtlas”, with part of these results and their implications also presented in Section 3.7.

Thus, in the case of historical measurements, it meant a direct comparison with individual SOC values associated with previously identified spatial regions or areas where new SOC samples were located. In contrast, for SOC estimates made by global prediction models, comparisons are made against corresponding point estimates at the exact locations and their confidence intervals, when available. The latter also served for upscale point-based reliability estimates from the existing soil maps to regional scales.

The workflow incorporated three datasets: WorldSoils, SoilGrids (van Wesemael et al., 2024; Poggio et al., 2021), and the extended SoilAtlas, based on the original Vojvodina soil atlas by Živković et al. (1972) (Živković et al., 1972), which served as the primary source of historical SOC data. More specific information about each selected data set and its adaptation for the inter-comparisons performed can be found in Supplementary S3.

When evaluating the specific accuracy of existing data sources and models, we have followed the methodology outlined in (Brus et al., 2017). Thus, we relied on individual differences between new measurements and their database counterparts, including squared, absolute and relative differences and their statistics over all sampling locations: Mean Bias Error (MBE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), when such information were available (e.g. like in the case of SoilAtlas historical SOC data) (Živković et al., 1972). Point estimates of global regression models, like WorldSoils (van Wesemael et al., 2024) and SoilGrids (Poggio et al., 2021), were compared in a similar manner against new measurements, with separate analyses for each of the time periods in which global regression models were designed (e.g., in the case of (van Wesemael et al., 2024) there were three models over the time span of five years).

Besides accuracy, the validity of the existing global regression models for the selected local area was also assessed by the coverage or reliability of their uncertainty estimates. This was tested by measuring how often newly collected SOC and BD samples fall within the model's confidence intervals. It also allowed mapping spatial variation in model uncertainty. Although WorldSoils (van Wesemael et al., 2024) and SoilGrids (Poggio et al., 2021) regression-based datasets also contain some original soil profiles for the selected area of interest (which can be regarded as relatively large and with high soil variability), there were only a few isolated samples available. Thus, local performance assessment of the existing regression models was of significant interest for determining the necessity for soil maps refinement, possible strategies, and future model updates.

On the other hand, historical data in SoilAtlas (Živković et al., 1972) were evaluated by comparing newly collected point observations with the SOC value ranges assigned to each soil subtype in the atlas. Namely, historical data in the digitized atlas were not assigned to specific locations but rather to larger spatial units defined by the identified soil subtype considered dominant within the spatial extent of the polygon drawn on the map. Thus, SOC inter-comparisons described in Supplementary S2 were not obtained by sampling the corresponding raster that could be derived from such atlas polygons, but rather by directly matching the corresponding soil subtypes from SoilAtlas (Živković et al., 1972) and soil subtypes of newly observed SOC samples. This was done because the soil subtype was a more reliable matching criterion than the spatial location of observed point samples and SoilAtlas polygons (Živković et al., 1972), since the soil subtype could be precisely determined for each new sample. Finally, map refinement strategies were explored through data fusion and cross-validation across sources. Similarly, acceptable uncertainty thresholds were defined for target application scenarios, ensuring alignment with end-user decision-making requirements.

3. Results

3.1. Overview of sampling strategy and cluster characteristics

3.1.1. Sampling strategy

A total of 186 samples for three types of analyses, corresponding to 186 sampling sites (30 m × 30 m plots) across 62 locations in the two targeted land cover classes—24 forest sites (72 samples) and 38 grassland sites (114 samples)—were collected. The 62 locations were selected from an initial pool of 3906 potential locations. The original proportional distribution of samples across selected classes was maintained, ensuring representativeness, and is well aligned with the coverage

proportions of 28.22% for forests and 46.86% for grasslands. Tables S1 and S2 in Supplementary Material S1 show the differences between actual and expected sample counts, along with their statistical significance. Further details on the sampling design, effort, and cluster zones can be found in sections 1.1 (“Sampling design and effort”) and 1.2 (“Sampling strategy and cluster zones”) of the Supplementary Material S1.

In total, 12 spatial clusters were established—six for forests and six for grasslands, Fig. 4a and b. Within forest areas, the cluster containing waterlogged stands (Forest cluster 0) was intentionally excluded to ensure consistent edaphic conditions and focus on non-riparian virgin or near-natural forest locations that best represent undisturbed reference conditions for surrounding agricultural fields. This resulted in 11 clusters that were sampled and taken into account for further analyses – five forest- and six grassland ones (Fig. 4).

The expected and actual numbers of sampling sites per cluster within classes are presented in Tables S1 and S2 in supplementary material S1. Sampling was evenly distributed between protected and non-protected areas, resulting in a 50:50 ratio.

3.1.2. Clusters characteristics

3.1.2.1. Land cover. Among all 62 sampling locations, in the field during our sampling campaign, only a few transitional types of Black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia*) correspond to self-sown forests of non-site-native trees (EUNIS category T1J) that were included in the forest category.

3.1.2.2. Soil characteristics. The differentiation between clusters was pronounced in soil texture, see details in Table 2.

- Forest (CLC Class 1) sites ranged from loams to sandy and clay loams.
- Grassland (CLC Class 3) sites showed greater variation, including sandy loams, saline clay loams, and alluvial loams.

3.1.2.3. Aridity assessment. Across the ten-year study period (2015–2024), a clear trend of increasing temperatures and decreasing precipitation is observed, leading to a corresponding decline in the De Martonne aridity index (IDM) for both forest and grassland clusters. Mean annual IDM cluster values range from 25.7 to 30.1 for grassland clusters and from 25.4 to 29.8 for forest clusters. In comparison with the ten years from 1950 to 1960 (Živković et al., 1972), the results show a substantial decrease in soil moisture across forest and grassland clusters, with most sites shifting to a drier category, for example, from humid to semi-humid conditions (Supplementary Material Table S3).

By integrating these descriptors for each spatial cluster, clear ecological differentiation along land-cover, soil texture, and aridity gradients emerges. This is shown in Table 2.

3.2. Determination of soil properties across ecosystems

Applied physical and chemical soil analysis provided detail characteristics of soil properties across forest and grassland ecosystems. The average carbon stock in forest soils was 62.54 t ha⁻¹, with an average SOC content of 2.00% and, while grassland soils showed an average carbon stock of 68.40 t ha⁻¹, with an SOC content of 2.05%. Details of soil properties across grassland and forest clusters from this study are presented in Table 3 and Supplementary material S1.5. The laboratory analyses were also considered in the context of the SOC stock trend and through SOC content comparisons across forests and grasslands, as presented in Sections 3.2 and 3.4, respectively.

SOC Stocks in forest soil. The assessment of SOC stocks at the selected forest locations revealed variation across the clusters (Table 3). Cluster 2 (Sandy-Loam Forest – Semi-Humid; SaLo-F-SH) had the highest SOC stock (73.56 t ha⁻¹), followed by Cluster 5 (Clay-Loam Forest –

Fig. 4. Cluster distribution within the forest soil class (a) and the grassland soil class (b).

Table 2

Overview of soil characteristics across aridity gradients.

Land cover	Cluster	Soil texture	Aridity category 1950-1960	Aridity category 2015-2024	Cluster name	Cluster label
Forest	1	Loam	Very humid	Humid	Loamy Forest – Humid	Loam-F-Hu
Forest	2	Sandy Loam	Humid	Semi-humid	Sandy-Loam Forest – Semi-Humid*	SaLo-F-SH
Forest	3	Sandy Loam	Humid	Humid	Sandy-Loam Forest – Humid	SaLo-F-Hu
Forest	4	Sandy Loam	Humid	Semi-humid	Sandy-Loam Forest – Semi-Humid*	SaLo-F-SH
Forest	5	Clay Loam	Humid	Humid	Clay-Loam Forest – Humid	ClLo-F-Hu
Grassland	0	Silt Loam	Humid	Humid	Silt-Loam Grassland – Humid	SiLo-G-Hu
Grassland	1	Loam	Humid	Semi-humid	Loamy Grassland – Semi-Humid*	Loam-G-SH
Grassland	2	Sandy Loam	Humid	Semi-humid	Sandy-Loam Grassland – Semi-Humid	SaLo-G-SH
Grassland	3	Saline Clay Loam	Humid	Semi-humid	Saline Clay-Loam Grassland – Semi-Humid	SaClLo-G-SH
Grassland	4	Loam	Humid	Semi-humid	Loamy Grassland – Semi-Humid*	Loam-G-SH
Grassland	5	Alluvial Loam	Humid	Semi-humid	Alluvial-Loam Grassland – Semi-Humid	AllLo-G-SH

F = Forest; G = Grassland; Hu = Humid; SH = Semi-Humid; Lo, Sa, Cl, Si = sand/clay/silt/loam components; *Clusters are labeled from the aridity and texture perspective but differed in their underlying characteristics because clustering was performed in the multidimensional feature space, including minimum temperature, total precipitation, average temperature at 2 m above ground, and minimum temperature soil order, type and texture.

Humid; ClLo-F-Hu, 69.31 t ha⁻¹), Cluster 1 (Loamy Forest – Humid; Loam-F-Hu, 68.26 t ha⁻¹), Cluster 4 (Sandy-Loam Forest – Semi-Humid; SaLo-F-SH, 63.45 t ha⁻¹), and Cluster 3 (Sandy-Loam Forest – Humid; SaLo-F-Hu, 47.49 t ha⁻¹).

SOC Stocks in grassland soil. The SOC stock assessment at the selected grassland locations revealed variation across clusters (Table 3). Cluster 3 (Saline Clay-Loam Grassland – Semi-Humid; SaLo-G-SH) had the highest SOC stock (83.82 t ha⁻¹), followed by Cluster 1 (Loamy Grassland – Semi-Humid; Loam-G-SH, 73.95 t ha⁻¹), Cluster 5 (Alluvial-Loam Grassland – Semi-Humid; AllLo-G-SH, 66.42 t ha⁻¹), Cluster 4 (Loamy Grassland – Semi-Humid; Loam-G-SH, 59.37 t ha⁻¹), Cluster 0 (Silt-Loam Grassland – Humid; SiLo-G-Hu, 52.69 t ha⁻¹), and Cluster 2 (Sandy-Loam Grassland – Semi-Humid; SaLo-G-SH, 19.38 t ha⁻¹).

3.3. SOC stock trend

The results of the SOCstock_{reference} change for the two analyzed periods are grouped by cluster and are shown in Table 4. The comparison of SOC stock change over roughly 70 years reveals an apparent decline in both classes across all clusters. Compared to soil under grassland, which shows an average SOC stock decrease of -0.82 t, the degradation process is more severe in forest soil, with a decline of -1.17 t. Within the forest soil class, the most significant SOC stock losses were observed in clusters 4 and 1. In the grassland soil class, the highest SOC losses were recorded in cluster 2 (Table 4).

Table 3
Results of the soil analyses based on new samples collected during 2024/2025.

Class	Forest					Grassland						
	Cluster	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	2	3	4	5
SOCstock [t ha ⁻¹]		68.26	73.56	47.49	63.45	69.31	52.69	73.95	19.38	83.82	59.37	66.42
SOC [%]		2.21	2.09	1.42	2.33	2.32	1.53	2.32	0.49	2.36	1.93	1.96
BD [g cm ⁻³]		0.99	1.21	1.16	0.91	1.00	1.16	1.11	1.30	1.20	1.07	1.15
Water holding capacity	-33 kPa [%]	31.31	23.26	13.94	24.96	34.19	14.65	30.45	8.43	34.11	33.32	33.79
	-625 kPa [%]	22.66	18.40	10.87	16.49	25.63	10.40	22.82	6.32	25.38	22.76	23.85
	-1500 kPa [%]	21.72	17.10	13.26	20.05	23.02	8.77	19.95	5.52	22.11	21.29	19.89
Total N [%]		0.19	0.18	0.12	0.20	0.20	0.13	0.20	0.04	0.20	0.17	0.17
Humus [%]		3.81	3.60	2.44	4.01	4.00	2.63	4.01	0.85	4.07	3.32	3.38
pH (H ₂ O)		6.49	7.34	7.59	7.86	6.41	7.49	7.49	7.97	6.96	7.47	7.65
CaCO ₃ [%]		1.31	2.22	3.04	13.74	0.63	2.66	3.88	3.29	1.66	3.04	6.21
PO ₄ -P [mg kg ⁻¹]		17.93	14.89	13.75	36.75	17.55	12.44	21.39	18.44	30.20	21.60	27.66
K ₂ O [mg100g ⁻¹]		17.80	14.71	9.55	26.41	20.32	13.36	22.28	8.72	34.55	31.05	26.19
CEC [meq 100g ⁻¹]		34.15	35.67	16.08	15.45	37.61	17.45	30.44	8.41	29.17	25.83	29.01
Coarse Sand [%]		11.68	13.02	13.36	22.37	14.16	9.17	12.53	6.27	11.10	6.18	8.83
Fine Sand [%]		45.47	63.05	74.11	55.27	35.59	75.83	54.35	86.23	43.37	48.89	41.78
Silt [%]		29.04	18.21	6.36	16.91	35.57	9.06	23.52	2.94	30.86	31.77	33.96
Clay [%]		13.81	5.72	6.17	5.46	14.68	5.94	9.60	4.57	14.67	13.15	15.44
Total Sand [%]		57.16	76.07	87.47	77.63	49.75	85.00	66.89	92.49	54.47	55.08	50.60
Silt + Clay [%]		42.84	23.93	12.53	22.37	50.25	15.00	33.11	7.51	45.53	44.92	49.40
8000-2000 μm [%]		42.38	37.65	13.68	27.28	49.59	12.13	39.06	2.07	45.04	40.32	48.73
2000-250 μm [%]		34.45	26.92	20.66	33.14	34.42	20.86	32.40	9.35	34.68	27.96	32.60
250-53 μm [%]		18.42	32.70	63.63	33.04	9.80	62.86	21.00	86.60	11.42	19.14	10.46
<53 μm [%]		4.75	2.73	2.03	6.54	6.19	4.15	7.54	1.99	8.86	12.58	8.21
MWD		2.54	2.24	1.01	1.79	2.88	0.94	2.35	0.34	2.66	2.36	2.82
Ks		1.50	4.21	0.55	3.52	2.28	0.42	4.25	0.22	2.41	2.67	4.21

Table 4
Comparative analysis of SOCstock_{reference} and its changes for the two observed periods.

Class	Cluster	SOCstock _{reference} (1950) [t]	SOCstock _{reference} (2024/2025) [t]	ΔSOCstock _{reference} [t]
Forest	1	6.74	5.40	-1.34
	2	6.56	5.96	-0.60
	3	6.95	5.88	-1.07
	4	6.76	4.82	-1.94
	5	6.64	5.74	-0.90
Grassland	0	6.51	5.66	-0.85
	1	6.62	6.05	-0.57
	2	6.62	4.78	-1.84
	3	6.49	6.09	-0.40
	4	6.57	5.96	-0.61
	5	6.62	5.95	-0.67

3.4. SOC content comparison across forest, grasslands and crop fields

The comparative analysis reveals apparent differences among the three land-use types shown in Fig. 5. Forests and grasslands exhibit higher SOC concentrations, with median values close to 2%, reflecting greater organic matter accumulation under natural vegetation. In contrast, croplands show notably lower SOC levels, with a median around 1.5% and a narrower distribution. The wider variability observed in forest and grassland samples indicates more heterogeneous conditions, whereas croplands exhibit more uniform, lower SOC levels due to long-term agricultural practices.

3.5. Landscape management and heterogeneity

The normalized Evenness and diversity Index (based on SDI) showed no significant difference between forest and grassland areas, with similar median values. However, grasslands exhibited a broader range and showed notably higher heterogeneity than forests, as expected given the generally greater diversity of landscape management patterns in our study region (Fig. 6).

3.6. Evaluation of SOC stock prediction models

This distribution of SOC stock across the clusters is also reflected in

Fig. 5. SOC distribution across forests, grasslands and croplands.

the distribution of average SOC content. The resulting thresholds,

Fig. 6. Boxplots of Shannon Diversity (a) and Shannon Evenness (b), illustrating landscape heterogeneity in forest and grassland sites.

defined as midpoints between the cluster centroids, delineate *low* (<47.40 t ha⁻¹), *medium* (47.40–74.68 t ha⁻¹), and *high* (>75.18 t ha⁻¹) SOC stock levels. According to these thresholds, the dataset includes 11 samples in the low, 29 in the medium, and 22 in the high SOC stock class. In the regression analysis, Elastic Net achieved the best performance among the tested algorithms, with a R² of 0.49 and RMSE of 13.74 t ha⁻¹. This indicates that the model explained about half of the variance in SOC stock across the study area, which can be considered a moderate level of predictive ability given the complexity of SOC dynamics and the relatively limited sample size. Random Forest Regressor and CatBoost Regressor performed similarly but did not surpass Elastic Net in predictive accuracy.

In contrast, the classification approach produced higher predictive reliability. Logistic Regression achieved the best results, with an overall accuracy (OA) of 76.90%, and macro F1-score of 77.10%. This solid performance suggests that while precise prediction of continuous SOC stock values remains challenging, classifying SOC stock into broader categories is more feasible. Random Forest achieved slightly lower accuracy, while CatBoost did not perform competitively. Nevertheless, macro F1-scores confirmed that Logistic Regression provided the most balanced classification across the three SOC stock classes. Normalized

confusion matrix demonstrates solid classification pattern, with the best results achieved for the *low* class and some misclassifications between the transitional classes *low - medium* and *medium - high*, Fig. 7. To reduce the effect of random variation in data splitting, the confusion matrix represents the average across five repeated cross-validation runs, providing a stable and representative estimate of model performance.

To quantify the importance of each feature, we used permutation importance on the final selected feature set for both regression and classification. Figs. 8 and 9 present the final set of features used in the models, sorted by their importance. To avoid fragmentation caused by one-hot encoding, categorical indicators were aggregated by their original categories, and significance was reported at the group level. The effect of each feature was measured as the average drop in the validation metric (a decrease in R² for regression and in macro F1-score for classification) after randomly permuting that feature's values, using 15 permutation repeats to ensure stable estimates.

The permutation importance analysis of the Elastic Net regression model indicates that Soil texture is by far the most influential predictor. Spatial clusters is the next most important group, reflecting clusters of forest and grassland categories. Grassland without tree/shrub cover, SDI, Soil groups and Soil type make a moderate contribution, while the remaining features have relatively small effects. These results suggest that most of the predictive information is carried by a few categorical groups.

In the Logistic Regression classification model, the contributions are more balanced. Soil texture again ranks highest, but Spatial clusters, Soil type, and Grassland without tree/shrub cover are close behind. The presence of sunflowers has a small effect, probably improving separation for one SOC stock class without affecting the whole model. Overall, the classifier appears to distribute importance across several feature groups rather than depending on a single dominant predictor, which is typically more robust for generalization than the regression model.

3.7. Evaluating the consistency between SOC content in-situ results and existing soil databases

Direct comparisons with point estimates from global regression models like WorldSoils (van Wesemael et al., 2024) and SoilGrids (Poggio et al., 2021) revealed higher individual and average RMSE values than those from the locally developed SoilAtlas (see details in Supplementary S2 and S3). To some degree, this behavior of global regression models was anticipated due to the lack of locally collected soil profiles or training samples. It may stem from their relatively poor

Fig. 7. Normalized confusion matrix illustrating the classification performance for *low*, *medium*, and *high* SOC stock classes.

Fig. 8. Permutation feature importance of final features of Elastic Net regression model.

Fig. 9. Permutation feature importance of final features of Logistic regression classification model.

adaptation to local soil specificities and variability across the large area of the Vojvodina region. In the following, Figs. 10–13 present some of the main results of SOC data analysis report provided in Supplementary S2, which presents detailed SOC data inter-comparison with the historical SoilAtlas information (Živković et al., 1972).

As shown in Fig. 10a, conducted range validation confirms that in many cases there is a significant discrepancy between the reported SoilAtlas SOC ranges and newly observed SOC values (when such SOC range information was available for the specific soil subtype in the SoilAtlas). The same also holds for Fig. 10c, in which the magnitudes of the corresponding relative differences in SOC values were analyzed. The direct comparison of SOC differences in Figs. 10b and 12b, c also indicates that, for some sampling locations, SoilAtlas SOC information associated with the same soil subtypes did not align with the new SOC values. Fig. 12a, along with the reported low correlation, also confirms this. To better understand the spatial distribution of the reported discrepancies, Fig. 12 provides a side-by-side comparison of SOC values between newly observed samples and SoilAtlas, for each of 186 sampling locations, using the same discrete colormap. Thus, in addition to amplitude differences, there are also differences in the spatial patterns of SOC values. These findings are also confirmed by the results of nonparametric SOC values density estimators in Fig. 13.

The presented results are accompanied by additional numerical estimates of SOC values MBE, MAE, and RMSE, tests of their statistical significance, bootstrap confidence intervals, and analysis of corresponding regression residuals against SoilAtlas SOC values. According to the report provided in Supplementary S2, 54.73 % of new SOC samples

were inside the SoilAtlas SOC range values, while the overall RMSE of 183 SOC value pairs was relatively high, with 0.93, and a confidence interval (CI) of [0.83, 1.04]. Similarly, MAE was estimated at 0.74 with CI of [0.66, 0.82]; MBE at -0.23 , [-0.35 , -0.09], while the percentage of the observed SOC samples with absolute relative differences smaller than 30 % (in comparison to SoilAtlas) was 46.99 %. MBE was shown to be statistically significantly different from zero. At the same time, the tests of MAE and MSE against the predefined threshold confirmed that both are statistically smaller than the median of the observed SOC samples. The Shapiro-Wilk test of the regression residuals from Fig. 11a confirmed that they follow a normal distribution. However, the corresponding coefficient of determination was very low, indicating that simple regression based on SoilAtlas cannot explain the variance in the observed SOC data. The link to the source code for the report and the presented diagrams is available in Supplementary S2.

4. Discussion

This study aimed to establish a spatially explicit SOC baseline for natural and semi-natural ecosystems in Vojvodina and to evaluate the applicability of regional datasets and modelling approaches for SOC assessment at the NUTS2 scale. Natural and semi-natural soils represent essential benchmarks for carbon accounting and restoration planning yet remain under-represented in regional datasets. Our results address existing gaps in soil data, particularly for natural and semi-natural habitats, and provide the first harmonized SOC baseline dataset in Vojvodina - natural soil reference system, serving as a regional

Fig. 10. Inter-comparison with the existing SoilAtlas database for each of 186 newly observed SOC samples (each row contains results corresponding to 9 unique SOC values); validation of the SoilAtlas SOC range values for each SOC sample (a); SOC differences between SOC_{atlas} (historical data) and SOC_{obs} (newly measured values) (b); validation of SOC values' absolute relative differences, when compared to SoilAtlas. For more information, please see the Supplementary S2 and accompanying code implementation.

Fig. 11. Scatter plot and simple linear regression between existing SoilAtlas SOC information and newly observed SOC samples (a). Reported Pearson correlation clearly indicates gap between point location SOC measurements and SOC values associated with SoilAtlas soil subtypes. Absolute and relative SOC values differences: (b) and (c), respectively. For more information, please see the Supplementary S2 and accompanying code implementation.

benchmark for natural soil conditions. The spatially stratified sampling framework we developed ensures that all strata (in our case, clusters) remain proportionally represented in each new sampling round, maintaining balanced ratios as the total sample size increases and providing a statistically robust, reproducible, and scalable design for long-term soil monitoring. By allocating additional samples to each stratum based on its expected share of the population (Equation (1)), the approach provides a consistent, statistically robust design for future soil sampling in natural and semi-natural areas. Inspired by the LUCAS approach (Ballin et al., 2022), the methodology was adapted to regional conditions by combining a 1×1 km grid with machine-learning-assisted clustering

based on soil, climate, and land-cover characteristics. This approach enables a more detailed assessment of SOC variability while maintaining compatibility with LUCAS, allowing the dataset to serve as a complementary regional data layer for existing monitoring systems (Panagos et al., 2025). Applying this framework supports the evaluation of long-term SOC dynamics in relation to historical land-use change in heterogeneous landscapes.

In our study region (Vojvodina), the large-scale conversion of natural vegetation to arable land over the past two centuries has led to pronounced SOC losses and changes in soil properties, particularly in the 0–30 cm layer, where root activity and carbon concentrations are

Fig. 12. Spatial locations and magnitudes of newly observed SOC samples (a) and corresponding SoilAtlas historical SOC data (b), with values matched by soil subtypes, not spatial locations. Groups in (b) correspond to SOC range values from (a), defined by SOC quantiles Q1-Q4. Spatially close sampling locations with the same numeric prefix identifier (ID) are shown as single points on the diagram, visually representing only the first of three unique values from the same area.

Fig. 13. Nonparametric distribution estimates of newly collected SOC samples (a) and their corresponding soil subtype SOC pairs from the SoilAtlas database (b), computed over the same range. The difference in distributions clearly indicates that historical SoilAtlas information is not fully capturing the range and magnitude of SOC variation in the population of newly collected SOC samples.

highest (Živković et al., 1972; Ćirić, 2014) (Tables 3 and 4; Fig. 5). Grasslands generally maintain higher SOC than forests due to greater organic matter inputs and accumulation under semi-arid conditions which is consistent with previously published results (Vasin et al., 2022), although comparisons show ongoing soil degradation in cultivated land (Ćirić et al., 2017; Vidojević, 2016), (Tables 2 and 3; Fig. 5). In parallel, human interventions— such as afforestation, peat enrichment, trenching, and nutrient amendments—have locally increased SOC in some locations. These changes interact with soil texture, moisture, and particle packing to modulate bulk density and carbon stocks (Table 3, Table S1.5). Overall, our observations confirm globally recognized soil-carbon relationships (Ernest et al., 2024) under the region’s increasingly arid climatic conditions, as documented in this study, and highlight the potential for targeted, nature-based management to enhance carbon sequestration and soil functioning across both sandy and clay-rich landscapes (Table 2).

Although SOC was measured within forests and grasslands, surrounding intensive agriculture and climate change have altered the broader environment, accelerating SOC loss. Protected forests on Fruška

Gora (cluster 5) and the Vršac Mountains (cluster 5) (Fig. 4) show lower losses. At the same time, salt-affected steppe soils experience minimal decline due to restricted use and low-intensity grazing (Životić and Vuković Vimić, 2022; Kašanin-Grubin et al., 2023). These results illustrate how both historical and ongoing land-use pressures shape SOC patterns (Table 4), emphasizing the need for context-aware management.

The study by Ćirić et al. (2020) (Ćirić et al., 2020) on five dominant soil types in Vojvodina showed that at the 0–30 cm depth, the highest soil organic carbon stocks occurred in Vertisols (99 t ha⁻¹), followed by Chernozems (79 t ha⁻¹), Solonetz (71 t ha⁻¹), Fluvisols (58 t ha⁻¹), and Arenosols (47 t ha⁻¹). In our analysis, the highest carbon stock values for both grasslands and forests were associated with clusters dominated by halomorphic soils, particularly Solonetz (cluster 3 in grasslands) and Arenosols of the Subotica Sands (cluster 2 in grasslands). In forests, the highest mean carbon stock was also recorded in cluster 2, corresponding to Arenosols in the Subotica Sand region. Halomorphic soils cover only ~10.6% of Vojvodina, are primarily used as pasture, and host halophytes and specialized microbial communities that maintain resilient

landscape features. Among these soils, Solonetz exhibits the highest regional carbon stocks (83.82 t ha^{-1}), consistent both with its soil type classification and with the cluster in which it is most represented. The high carbon content in Solonetz surface layers reflects the dominance of grass vegetation, which promotes the accumulation of humus in a thin top horizon (Ćirić et al., 2020). Conversely, Arenosols in the Subotica Sands are naturally low in fertility, but nearly two centuries of afforestation (Živković et al., 1972) have enhanced humification and increased carbon stocks in these soils.

Compared with the LUCAS landscape diversity assessment across Europe (LUCAS Statistics Explained), the values of landscape heterogeneity indices reported in our study appear relatively low. This conclusion is expected given our aim of assessing typical forest and grassland landscapes (see Fig. 2b), which implies that these landscapes are somewhat uniform. Their uniformity reflects their relatively undisturbed condition, which is one of the reasons soils at these locations show higher SOC values than disturbed, agricultural soils. Nevertheless, uniformity itself does not imply high SOC, considering that agricultural settings can also be highly uniform. Our statement simply reflects that, in natural ecosystems, “pristine” usually implies the absence of elements that disrupt the spatial continuity of a forest or grassland patch. This also means that in these ecosystems organic matter inputs and soil structure develop under relatively undisturbed conditions, opposed to typical agricultural settings, that are considered highly disturbed and, in which, SOC content is lower.

Machine learning prediction models revealed that SOC stock variability is meaningfully associated with a set of environmental conditions, such as diversity indicators and soil properties. However, by conducting this analysis, we demonstrated that SOC stock is challenging to predict as a continuous variable, with only moderate predictive capability. In contrast, classification into discrete SOC stock classes provided considerably higher accuracy and more balanced performance, suggesting that SOC stock can be more reliably distinguished across classes than estimated as a continuous variable. Higher performance of the classification models is expected because converting SOC stocks into classes simplifies the prediction task and reduces sensitivity to small differences in the target values. As a result, classification shifts the objective from precise value estimation to the discrimination of SOC stock levels, which generally leads to more, stable and balanced performance. Overall, the results indicate that the selected predictors are more effective in capturing differences among SOC stock levels than in explaining variability in continuous SOC stock values.

Analysis of the results showed almost no confusion between the low and high classes, indicating that the model successfully separates the extreme SOC stock levels. Across the remaining misclassified instances, there is a roughly balanced distribution between overestimates and underestimates. In several overestimated cases (true = low/medium but predicted = medium/high), the model assigns a higher SOC stock class because the combination of environmental predictors, such as diversity indicators and soil properties, suggests conditions typically associated with higher SOC stock levels (Mauki et al., 2023). As noted, when visiting these sites, many may have experienced more intensive or variable land management in the past (Venteris et al., 2004; Grandy and Robertson, 2007), which could explain the difference between the field-measured SOC stock and the model predictions. Possible limitations in the soil texture data are that a significant predictor of SOC may also contribute more generally to both types of misclassifications, as mapped texture classes do not always perfectly reflect fine-scale conditions at the sampling point (Hamzehpour et al., 2019). The underestimated cases (true = medium/high but predicted = low/medium) may be particularly affected by this issue. Since soil texture was identified as the most influential predictor in the model (Figs. 8 and 9), any mismatch between mapped and actual field conditions may lead the model to assign a lower SOC class than that observed in the field. A more accurate and spatially detailed representation of soil texture would therefore likely improve model performance. However, because soil

texture is not easily mapped directly using remote sensing data, complementary predictors may also be useful. In this regard, habitat maps may provide additional support, as they are commonly derived from a combination of vegetation, land-use, and environmental characteristics, including soil-related properties, thereby helping to better represent spatial patterns relevant to SOC variability.

In contrast, historical data in SoilAtlas (Živković et al., 1972) did not represent point measurements from specific locations but rather values associated with particular soil subtypes within spatial polygons identified in previous studies. This somewhat limits the interpretation of the data quality metrics since there was no direct location correspondence between in-situ SOC measurements and the data available in SoilAtlas (Živković et al., 1972). Nevertheless, inter-comparison with the existing databases clearly showed that in-situ results were better aligned with historical data (Živković et al., 1972) than globally derived regression estimates (van Wesemael et al., 2024; Poggio et al., 2021), thereby prioritizing historical data from (Živković et al., 1972) as the more reliable source of information in this study. The reason for this stems from the scale of this study was conducted at regional vs. global models. For the regional scale, a data-deficient one as well, global models simply lacked the accuracy needed due to a very low number of available local samples. This result further emphasizes the importance of locally derived soil datasets for reliable SOC estimation at regional scales.

Taken together, our results demonstrate that spatially stratified soil sampling combined with machine-learning modelling provides a robust and scalable framework for assessing SOC stocks in natural ecosystems. The study establishes the first harmonized natural SOC baseline dataset (natural soil reference system) for forests and grasslands in Vojvodina and shows that locally derived soil data are more appropriate than global regression estimates when applied at the regional (NUTS2) scale. These findings highlight the importance of regionally grounded soil monitoring systems for supporting nature-based climate solutions, spatial planning, and long-term soil management.

This study established the first harmonized SOC baseline for natural and semi-natural ecosystems in Vojvodina using a spatially stratified sampling framework and machine-learning-assisted analysis. SOC stocks in forests and grasslands were comparable, but consistently higher than those typically reported for intensively cultivated croplands, highlighting the importance of natural vegetation for maintaining soil carbon stocks. Comparison with historical datasets revealed a long-term decline in SOC stocks across the region, reflecting the combined effects of land-use change and increasing aridity. Discrepancies between locally derived measurements and global SOC datasets highlight the need for regionally calibrated soil monitoring systems. The resulting Natural-Soil reference framework provides a baseline for evaluating future SOC dynamics and supports regional soil monitoring, carbon accounting, and spatial planning for nature-based climate solutions. These findings provide a basis for further development of regional soil monitoring systems.

Several limitations should be acknowledged, particularly regarding the input data used for sampling design and modelling. One limitation concerns the thematic resolution of the land-use data used for clustering. While CORINE Land Cover provided the most suitable available dataset for this study, the use of a more detailed classification, such as an EUNIS Level 3 habitat map, could further improve the ecological specificity of the clusters; however, such data are currently not available for the study area. Although the sampling design ensures regional representativeness, the number of sampling locations may still be insufficient to fully capture fine-scale spatial variability. Increasing the sample size would likely provide a more detailed representation of SOC patterns, particularly for machine-learning applications. Model predictions are also subject to uncertainties related to the availability and spatial resolution of key predictors, especially soil properties. In addition, the lack of detailed information on historical land management practices may limit the model's ability to fully explain SOC variability.

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mitigation, but effective management requires accurate monitoring from local to regional scales. Further development of regional soil monitoring systems will benefit from the integration of harmonized sampling frameworks and advances in digital soil mapping. Expanding soil data availability and improving spatial resolution are essential for more accurate SOC assessment and for supporting targeted management interventions. In this context, the framework presented in this study provides a scalable approach for linking local SOC measurements with regional monitoring efforts and broader climate and land-use policies.

However, comprehensive soil data remains limited in the Western Balkans (Zdruli et al., 2022), underscoring the importance of local reference datasets like the one presented in this study, which is critical to supporting regional policy and management. Harmonized monitoring networks, such as the LUCAS program (European Soil Data Centre, 2025) provide valuable pan-European in situ data, and continuous, integrated soil assessment systems, enriched by modern sensing technologies (Wadoux et al., 2020) can serve as “living” soil registries. Our results help fill current data gaps, providing a foundation for improved soil management (Belay et al., 2025), spatial planning, and nature-based climate solutions in Vojvodina.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tijana Nikolić Lugonja: Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Kristina Kalkan:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Miljana Marković:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Branko Brkljač:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Sanja Brdar:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Predrag Lugonja:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Sreten Terzić:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Andrijana Andrić:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Maja Knezević:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indic.2026.101325>.

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Data availability

Data will be published in Data in brief and before that it will be available on request

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